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Socio-Demographic Correlates Of Prevalence Of Work Stress Among Academic Staff Of Public Universities In Rivers State, Nigeria

¹Prof Azuonnwu, Goodluck & ²Asuk, Faith Matthew

¹Highstone Global University, Texas

goodator2002@yahoo.com

²Department of Human Kinetics, Health and Safety Education,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State, Nigeria

Correspondence author: Asuk Faith

ABSTRACT

Stress among academic staff is a serious public health problem challenging effectiveness and efficiency of academic staff in Nigeria. This study investigated the socio-demographic correlates of the prevalence work stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. The study population comprised of 3,983 academic staff in the three government owned Universities in Rivers State. The sample size was 768 and a multistage sampling procedure was adopted to select the respondents. The instrument for data collection was an adopted questionnaire titled, Questionnaire on Work Stress (QWS)". The instrument consisted of two sections which reflected the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, and academic stressors Data analysis was carried out using percentage and Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that, the prevalence of stress among academic staff was high (95.3%). Statistically significant relationship was found between stress and factors such as marital status (N = 747, r = 0.41, p = 0.02). However, the result showed a non-significant relationship between stress and gender (N = 747, r = 0.24, p = 0.17) and family size (N = 747, r = 0.05, p = 0.11). The study concluded that the prevalence of stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was high, which could be correlated with marital status. It was recommended among others that the government should interface with the academic staffs in the Universities to find out what needs to be done and implement same urgently to ease the stress on the academic staffs.

Keywords: Correlates, Prevalence, Work Stress, Socio-demographic, Staff.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is inevitable in every works of life, though it may differ in its intensity depending on the nature of work. Occupational stress among academic staffs is a key public health issue in today's world because it can reduce their efficiency and the effectiveness of their academic work, alongside its effects on their health and general well-being. According to Newberry and Allsop (2017), the academic world is a highly stressful occupation. This is also shown in the high prevalence of stress among academic staffs of public universities around the world reported in different empirical studies. Kabito et al. (2020) reported a prevalence of 60.4% among academic staffs in Ethiopia. In Malaysia Mz et al. (2016) reported 60.8%, China (91.0%) reported by Sun et al. (2014), India (74%) (Reddy & Poornima, 2014), Tanzania, (75%) (Mkumbo, 2014), and Botswana (81.0%) (Fako, 2014). In Nigeria, Atunde et al. (2020) reported from a study on the occupational-related stress that over 75% University Staff experienced stress.

The right level of stress tends to promote effective functioning of the body and the mind, while numerous stress especially if prolonged, distresses the body and can result into physical and mental illness (Asogwa, 2017). Stress can be physical, social, emotional, intellectual, and occupational which is the focus of this study. Physically, stress threatens the physiological homeostasis of an individual (Biohanu et al., 2018). Emotionally, stress causes negative feeling about self which may result into low self-esteem, feeling of anxiety depression and other mental health conditions (Belachew et al., 2017). Socially, stress alters interpersonal relationships (Ganster & Rosen, 2014). Intellectually stress affect the problem solving perception abilities of a person (Jerard, 2018). Stress has been conceptualized differently by different authors. Occupational stress is the stress experienced by an individual due to the job done. Occupation is a set of tasks people engage in to meet their self-maintenance, expression and fulfillment in life (Chan & Pang, 2019). According to Zeller and Levin (2014), occupational stress involves the interaction of work and worker characteristics as well as personal stressors such as family responsibilities, lack of sleep, and personal resources (e.g., conflict-resolution management, health promotion practices) that influence nurses' appraisal of and coping with workplace situations. Job stress is the process that arises when work demands of various types and combinations exceed or do not match the employee's capacity and capability (McVicar et al., 2014). However, stress could be as a result of multiple factors which were included in this study as associated factors such as: workload, poor remuneration, job requirement, unavailability of facilities and equipment, unconducive work environment, gender role, marital status and family size.

Family size is one factor which could contribute to stress among individuals including academic staffs as it may require them to put extra effort to be able to meet up with family demands as well as job demands. Particularly when the family size is large (Mackira & Palamuleni, 2017). The study of Alosaimi et al. (2018) buttress that having large family size was significantly associated with stress. Most workers like lecturers encountered several expectations which the family members, especially those with large family size, peer, superior and subordinates have from the employee. Failure to understand such expectations or to convey such expectations lead to role ambiguity/role conflict which in turn causes stress. Such stress could be easily managed or handled if the individual is in a marital relationship with a good spouse who helps to ease the stress.

Marital status could mean an individual's state of marital relationship either, single, married, cohabiting, separated, divorced or widowed. For the married female academicians, if their work is given greater priority at the expense of the family, they are running a risk of losing the home. Hence, adequate support should be provided for lecturers in order to function well in the system. On the contrary, Anbu (2015) posited that, the female higher institution lecturers who are married have more stress than the male lecturers. The reason is that married lecturers apart from guiding the school students, have to look after their family members, they were not able to allocate equal weight age to working as well as family environment, hence this result in enhanced stress level, particularly for the female lecturers.

Gender role continues to influence health behaviour. As regards stress and gender, Antoniou et al. (2014) in their study on occupational stress and professional burnout in lecturers found that, female lecturers experience more stress and lower personal accomplishment than men due to their gender roles both in the family and society. The problems of lecturers particularly females seem compounded because of the sex-role stereotyping in which power and independence are not traditionally assigned to the Nigerian women. Specifically, the Nigerian female lecturer has the peculiar problem of having to cope with the role of the token women (a woman to be seen but not heard), lack of role models to learn from, feelings of isolation, the strain of coping with male prejudices and overt or covert discriminations from senior colleagues (Nnabuife et al., 2014). These stresses and stress-related outcomes do have serious consequences on the female lecturer's personal, mental, psychological and physical health. Routine check needs to be given its own place for the lecturer to maintain a good health status (Akinsanya, 2014). Females as well as male experience stress but its burden may be more on the females because of their double responsibility of been lecturers as well as home keepers.

Occupational stress is a serious threat to health of academic staff and can cause hostility, aggression, absenteeism, and turnover and negatively affect their productivity (Mosadeghrad et al., 2014). Occupational stress has proven to be detrimental on academic staff's physical and psychological health including cardiovascular and pulmonary diseases, musculoskeletal disorders, anxiety,

depression, and psychological distress, to name a few. The impacts of job stress cost healthcare organization millions, if not, billions of dollars annually due to absenteeism and staff turnover (Kinnunen-Amoroso, 2014; Arsalani et al., 2014; Ayed et al., 2014). The fact that stress can make people ill and is implicated in the prevalence and development of coronary heart disease, mental illness, certain types of cancer, smoking, dietary problems, excessive alcohol consumption and substance abuse, life dissatisfaction, accident and unsafe behavior at work, migraine, stomach ulcers, hay fever, asthma and skin rashes, marital and family problems.

Stress among academic staff is a serious public health problem challenging effectiveness and efficiency of academic staff in Nigeria, particularly those in the public universities affected by incessant strike. Such stress could present certain consequences such as anxiety, depression, cardiac arrest and even death. The effects of stress among academic staff may even become worse by various factors surrounding them, including those in Rivers State, such as non-payment of allowances, promotion benefits, research grants, welfare packages and poor working environment. Given the disproportionate ratio of students to lecturers in universities in Rivers State, many are over bordered with excessive workload with the resultant stress. This is even worsened in the public universities where many lecturers are assigned to several tasks with unconducive working conditions leading to lack of privacy, and both mental and emotional disturbances which all contribute to the occupational stress confronting them. Occupational stress is associated with a number of health problems including high blood pressure, diabetes, anxiety, depression, fever, headache cardiovascular disease, and irritable bowel syndrome among those who experience it. However, socio-demographic characteristics of the workers could play a role in the level of stress academic staff experience which the researcher intends to find out. Hence, this study focused on the socio-demographic correlates of prevalence of work stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State. The study following research questions were raised for the study:

1. What is the prevalence of stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State
2. There is no significant relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State
3. There is no significant relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. The study population comprised of 3,983 academic staff in the three government owned Universities in Rivers State namely: University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The sample size was 768 and a multistage sampling procedure was employed to select the respondents. In the first stage, a simple random sampling technique was used to select five faculties in each of the Universities; at the second stage, the simple random sampling technique was also used to select ten departments (from each selected faculty) in each of the selected Universities; at the third stage, the simple random sampling was used to select the determined number of respondents from each institution. The instrument for data collection in this study was an adopted questionnaire titled, "Questionnaire on Stress and its Determinant Factors (QSiDF)". The instrument consisted of two sections. Section A addressed the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. It consisted of five items on a multiple response format which include; age, gender, marital status, family size and years of work experience. Section B focused was designed to elicit responses on academic stressors

on a modified scale rated under four categories of responses ranging from: causing no stress (0), mild stress (1), moderate stress (2), and causing severe stress (3) to indicate intensity of stress caused by each item. Data analysis was carried out using percentage and Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results of the study are shown below:

Table 1: Percentage distribution showing the prevalence of stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Prevalence of stress	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Severe	222	29.7
Moderate	374	50.1
Mild	116	15.5
No stress	35	4.7
Total	747	100.0

Table 1 revealed the percentage distribution showing the prevalence of stress among academic staff. The result revealed that more than three quarter 374(50.1%) had moderate level of stress, 222(29.7%) had severe stress, 116(15.5%) had mild stress, while very few 35(4.7%) had no stress. Thus, the prevalence of stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was high (95.3%).

Table 2: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Gender	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.24	Low relationship
	N	747	747	
Gender	Pearson correlation	0.24	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 2 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.24$, indicating a low relationship. Thus, the relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was moderate.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Marital status	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.41	Moderate relationship
	N	747	747	
Marital status	Pearson correlation	0.41	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 3 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.41$, indicating a moderate relationship. Thus, the relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was moderate.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Family size	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.05	Very low relationship
	N	747	747	
Family size	Pearson correlation	0.05	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 4 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.05$, indicating a very low relationship. Thus, the relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was very low.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 5: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Gender	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.24	H_0 not rejected
	Sig.		0.17*	
	N	747	747	
Gender	Pearson correlation	0.24	1	
	Sig	0.17*		
	N	747	747	

***Not Significant; $p > 0.05$**

Table 5 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between gender and stress among academic staff as $p > 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = 0.24$, $p = 0.17$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between gender and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was not rejected.

Table 6: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Marital status	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.41	H_0 rejected
	Sig.		0.02*	
	N	747	747	
Marital status	Pearson correlation	0.41	1	
	Sig	0.02*		
	N	747	747	

***Significant; $p < 0.05$**

Table 6 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff as $p < 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = 0.41$, $p = 0.02$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between marital status and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was rejected.

Table 7: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Family size	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.05	H ₀ not rejected
	Sig.		0.11*	
	N	747	747	
Family size	Pearson correlation	0.05	1	
	Sig.	0.11*		
	N	747	747	

***Not Significant; p>0.05**

Table 7 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between family size and stress among academic staff as $p > 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = 0.05$, $p = 0.11$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between family size and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study showed that the prevalence of stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was high (95.3%). This finding is was not surprising because teaching in the university is highly demanding due to certain factors such as large amount of content to teach, time pressure to meet deadlines, work overload, doing work that mentally straining, and demand for constant paper/seminar presentations; this coupled with work demands affect personal and home life. This finding corroborates that of Gheshlagh et al. (2017) whose study on the prevalence of stress in Iran showed a prevalence of stress as high as 99.1%. The finding of this study also gives credence to others such as Teixeira et al. (2016) which showed a high prevalence of stress. The finding of this study is also in keeping with findings from the study of Adzakpah et al. (2018) which also revealed a very high level of stress among the academic staffs of universities. The similarity of the stressors faced by the respondents in the previous studies and the present one might be implicated for the similarity found between the previous and present study. However, the finding of the study differs from that of Yusoff and Rahim (2020) whose study on the prevalence and sources of stress among medical trainees in Malaysia showed a low prevalence of 36.4%. This variance could be attributed to the difference in the study population. The present study focused on academic staffs in universities who are saddled with the responsibility of teaching, while the previous study focused on medical trainees who are students, thus, may not be exposed to the same stress level due to the role difference between the two groups of subjects studies. Also, the difference in the study location could also be implicated for the variation found between both studies.

The finding of the study revealed that the relationship between gender and stress was low, and was not statistically significant ($N = 747$, $r = 0.24$, $p = 0.17$). Though no significant difference was found but severe stress was found more among females than males. This could be due to the dual role of the females running a postgraduate programme and also keeping the home added to work or business she is doing to support the family financially. The finding of this study is akin to Kim et al. (2018) who noted that women suffer a higher level of gender dissemination than men that leads to stress at the workplace ($P = 0.01$) and are less likely to manage work-related stress. The result of this study is in contraindication with studies of Desio et al. (2017) that significant difference between male at $P = 0.009$ as compared to female. This similarity could be explained by the similarity in the study design.

The result indicated that the relationship between marital status and stress was moderate, and was statistically significant ($N = 747$, $r = 0.41$, $p = 0.02$). The finding of this study is akin to that of Onowhakpor (2018) whose study in Ghana found that the sources of stress are high for workers with high workload. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Segal et al. (2016) who found that some of the major sources of occupational stress affects workers may be more severe for those with pressing workload. The finding of this study corroborates that of Nwokeoma et al. (2019) whose study on work-related stress management among Nigeria public workers which showed that respondents stress level had a statistically significant relationship with marital status but the married are more stress. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Shimazu et al. (2013) whose study on stress

management programme in Japan showed that, the respondents had high interest in stress management among which high interest was found among all the respondents in all category of marital status. The finding of this study corroborates that Abu-Helalah, et al. (2014) which showed significant relationship between between marital status and stress. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Shimazu et al. (2013) whose study on stress management programme in Japan showed that, there was a statistically significant relationship between marital status and stress. The finding of this study corroborates that Abu-Helalah et a. (2014) which showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between between marital status and stress. The similarity between the present study and that of Nwokeoma and colleagues could be due to the homogeneity of the study population.

The result showed that the relationship between family size and stress was very low, and was not statistically significant. The finding of this study corroborates that of Nwokeoma et al. (2019) whose study on the impact of occupational health coaching on work-related stress management among Nigeria public workers which showed relationship between family size and stress. The finding of this study is in line with that of Gebrekirstos (2015) where the result indicated that there was a relationship between family size and stress. The finding of this study is in line with that of Shimazu et al. (2013) whose study on stress management programme in Japan showed that, there was a relationship between family size and stress. The finding of this study is also in line with that of Oyewole and Popoola (2019) study on Occupational Stress and Coping Strategies among Lecturers in Nigerian Universities which showed there was a relationship between family size and stress. The study revealed that lecturers experience moderate levels of occupational stress, with workload and family size being the major stressors. Similarly, Adebayo (2017) undertook a study on Occupational Stress and Coping Strategies among Nigerian University Lecturers. The study found that Nigerian university lecturers experience moderate levels of occupational stress and there was a relationship between family size and stress. The finding of this study is also in line with that of Adeyemi-Bello, and Ogunyemi, (2018) study carried out on Occupational Stress among Academic Staff in Nigerian Universities which showed a there was a relationship between family size and stress. This similarity could be attributed to the homogeneity of the study population as they were both focused on individuals dealing with studies, this might be implicated for the similarities found, specifically, university academic staffs. This might be implicated for the similarities found between the previous studies and the present study.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that the prevalence of stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was high, which was correlated mainly by marital status.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The government should interface with the academic staffs in the Universities to find out what needs to be done and implement same urgently to ease the stress on the academic staffs.
2. School administrators should also make the work environment less stressful for both males and female lecturers, by devising techniques to create and maintain optimal stress levels among them for purposes of improving and maintaining their health.
3. The school management should give preference to married lecturers especially the pregnant ones in terms of assigning of duty, which should be done in such a way that will not over burden them and add to the stress they face at home.
4. The academic staffs should also make conscious effort to ensure they reduce stress at home, particularly those with large family size.

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